

Wild foods used to improve eye sights

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Abstract: Eye problems are prevalent, especially among the elderly. Local plants have been traditionally used to treat various eye issues, but this knowledge is at risk of being lost. To address this, a literature survey was conducted, revealing 15 plants with potential therapeutic benefits for improving eyesight. Notably, most of these plants are herbaceous. Further research on these plants could lead to the development of effective therapeutic agents.

Keywords: Eye problems, ethnobotany, local plant parts

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 2.2 billion people worldwide suffer from various eye problems (Vashist et al., 2022), with around 1 billion individuals lacking access to advanced medical treatment or remaining untreated. The prevalence of chronic diseases, such as diabetes, is exacerbating the issue, contributing to a rising number of eye-related cases (Clare et al., 2024). Inadequate nutrition is also a significant contributing factor. Historically, people had better vision and fewer eye problems, likely due to a combination of positive biotic and abiotic factors, a diet rich in organic foods and wild nutraceuticals, and traditional knowledge of local bioresources for treating eye issues (Puri et al., 2022; Kropp et al., 2023). However, urbanization, increased access to allopathic medicine, and biodiversity loss are eroding this traditional wisdom. Documenting this knowledge is crucial for developing sustainable, healthy lives and discovering new treatments for various eye

problems. This review aims to gather scattered information on plant-based remedies for eye issues, providing a foundation for future research and potential drug development.

Methodology

For present study, different types of published reports, research papers, review papers and exploration reports were used to gather the information. Platforms like Springer, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Academia or also used to search the information (Shayanfar et al., 2019; Santana-Garrido et al., 2020; Nafees et al., 2022; Andary et al., 2025).

Results and discussion

Literature survey revealed that about 15 plant species are used to treat different types of eye problems belonging to 13 family and 15 genera (Table 1; Figure 1). It was observed that among the enumerated species, 4 species of fruits are used followed by whole plant (3 species), seed (3 species), rhizome (3 species), bulb and leaf (1 species). After analysis of Table 1, maximum plants are herbaceous, which are used to cure eye problems. These plants can be used for further advanced research works. Other researchers are also documented the medicinal plants used to cure eye problems. Some enumerated species like *Olea europaea*, *Acorus calamus* L., *Ocimum basilicum* L. etc. (Shayanfar et al., 2019; Santana-Garrido et al., 2020).

Table 1: Plants used in different eye problems

Plant Name	Family	Uses	Source
<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L. (Figure 2)	Fabaceae	The seeds are used to delay the progression of cataract.	Nafees et al., (2022) (Figure 2)
<i>Acorus calamus</i> L.	Acoraceae	The fruits are used as kohl for clear vision.	Shayanfar et al., (2019)
<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Liliaceae	The bulb is used to improve visual acuity	Andary et al., (2025)
<i>Atropa bella-donna</i> L.	Solanaceae	The macerated fruits are topically used to treat ocular disease.	Nafees et al., (2022)
<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	Asteraceae	The plant juice is used to treat eye irritation	Andary et al., (2025)
<i>Coptis teeta</i> Wall.	Ranunculaceae	Traditionally, the rhizomes are used in eye diseases.	Nafees et al., (2022)
<i>Crocus sativus</i> L.	Iridaceae	Dried stigmas of flowers are used to increase the visual acuity.	Nafees et al., (2022)

<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L. (Figure 3)	Cyperaceae	The rhizome decoction is used to reduce ocular discharges	Andary et al., (2025) (Figure 3)
<i>Datura stramonium</i> L. (Figure 4)	Solanaceae	The seed extraction is used to treat mydriasis.	Andary et al., (2025) (Figure 4)
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	Leaf juice used orally to improve the vision power	Shayanfar et al., (2019)
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i> Mill.	Apiaceae	The seeds are used to improve the vision.	Nafees et al., (2022)
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Lamiaceae	Whole plant juice is used as an eye drop.	Shayanfar et al., (2019)
<i>Olea europaea</i> L.	Oleaceae	Fruits are used to improve the eye sight.	Santana-Garrido et al., (2020)
<i>Vitis vinifera</i> L.	Vitaceae	The fruits are used to improve eye sight.	Shayanfar et al., (2019)
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	Zingiberaceae	The rhizomes are used to treat diabetic retinopathy	Nafees et al., (2022)

Figure 1: Uses (%) of plant parts

Figure 2: Fruits of *Abrus precatorius*

Figure 3: Habitat and flowers of *Cyperus rotundus*

Figure 4: Leaves and flowers of *Datura stramonium*

Conclusion

In today's context, eye problems affect people of all ages, and while allopathic treatments are readily available, there is a growing need to explore sustainable, locally sourced therapeutic agents rooted in indigenous traditional knowledge. This study provides an overview of 15 plant species, belonging to 13 families and 15 genera, that are traditionally used to improve eyesight and alleviate related issues. Scientific validation of these plants could lay the groundwork for developing effective treatments for various eye problems, offering a promising avenue for further research and discovery.

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